

Scaling green transitions: using social listening to explore Green Deal online discourse across Europe

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Executive Summary

Set within the context of the EU Green Deal's ambitions to achieve a more sustainable future for Europe, the SHARED GREEN DEAL project undertook social experiments to test and trial different approaches for achieving sustainability. These experiments were developed to align with six Green Deal priority areas, namely: Clean Energy; Circular Economy; Efficient Renovations; Sustainable Mobility; Sustainable Food; and Preserving Biodiversity. The 24 social experiments undertaken within the project also provided the opportunity to explore the implications of sustainability transitions on broader, cross-cutting themes, specifically: Gender and Diversity; Geographic and Institutional Differences; Governance Agendas; Justice, Vulnerability and Inequality; and Societal Challenges.

Whilst a range of stakeholders were involved in the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments, insights related to the EU Green Deal topics were limited to the individuals across the 24 experiment sites. As such, the perspectives of some stakeholders and insights from certain locations were not captured through the experiment activities. To help address this, and ensure that the SHARED GREEN DEAL project was exposed to a range of discourse around EU Green Deal topics, a social listening analysis was undertaken.

The Meltwater platform was used to conduct the social listening analysis. The intention of social listening is to capture conversations, trends, and sentiments around particular topics that are expressed across social media platforms and other online spaces. Using recommendations generated as part of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project as a foundation, search strings were designed to retrieve informal, organic, online discourse about the six experiment streams and five cross-cutting themes of the project. These searches were translated into 10 European languages, helping cover countries which did not host in-person experiments.

Key topics of online discourse were identified for each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams and cross-cutting themes. Examples of online discourse topics related to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams include: knowledge-sharing to support more sustainable practices; discussions around particular technologies and actions that need to be undertaken to achieve a sustainable society; and reflections on the resources and initiatives required to support the achievement of desired futures. The analysis of the cross-cutting themes highlighted the importance of engaging with thematic topics to achieve sustainability transitions across sectors, manifesting in discourse around citizen engagement in decision-making; support for grassroots initiatives across Europe; and the need to ensure legislation is designed to work for everyone.

By bringing together the insights obtained through the social listening activity and the experiences of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, a number of implications for European policy have been identified. In summary: the need to move away from isolated interventions and focus on supporting local capacity to achieve sustainability ambitions; the importance of creating flexible policies that allow for EU-to-local translation at the national level; and, the opportunities associated with multi-level governance systems, and the role for NGOs and trusted networks within this.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Introducing the *SHARED GREEN DEAL* project

The EU Green Deal was launched in 2019, setting out a plan “to transform Europe’s economy, energy, transport, and industries for a more sustainable future” (European Commission, N.D.). A number of plans and policies have been developed to support the achievement of this ambition, including those related to financing clean investments (NextGenerationEU, REPowerEU), supporting a just transition (Just Transition Fund, EU solidarity fund), industrial competitiveness (Green Deal Industrial Plan), and circular economy (Zero Pollution Action Plan), amongst others. Both the broader Green Deal ambition and related mechanisms highlight the need to change existing practices and systems to achieve a more sustainable future. Yet recent discourse is arguing that the Green Deal needs to be updated and “recalibrated” to align with the current sociopolitical, environment, and economic context (European Economic and Social Committee, 2024). Through the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, we have undertaken social experiments to test and trial different approaches for achieving the Green Deal, with these experiments situated within local, national and European contexts.

The social experiments were designed to address behavioural, social, and cultural dimensions of the EU Green Deal. In total, 24 local interventions across Europe were designed and implemented, which brought together diverse stakeholders to explore alternative approaches for supporting the transition to a more sustainable Europe. Each intervention was situated within the local context in which they were undertaken, meaning that local needs, priorities and ambitions were considered.

Each experiment stream had four local interventions, one from each of Northern, Southern, Eastern and Western Europe. Over the course of a year, the local interventions used different participatory methods of supporting changes towards a more sustainable future – see Table 1, with these interventions being grounded within local context. Based upon the experiences of these practical interventions, recommendations were developed on how to utilise the learnings to progress towards a more sustainable future.

Table 1: A table summarising the focus of each experiment stream and the locations where the interventions were undertaken

Experiment stream	Intervention focus	Experiment locations
Clean Energy	Visions of desirable energy futures were co-created with the local community through dialogue events.	Ærø, Denmark Granada, Spain Belchatow, Poland Essex, UK
Circular Economy	Circular economy concepts were introduced to local businesses and the adoption of circular economy practices monitored.	Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus Santo Tirso, Portugal Ljubljana, Slovenia Val-de-Marne, France
Efficient Renovations	Knowledge networks were developed to share knowledge and know-how about renovation between citizens and professionals.	Nógrád County, Hungary Mayo, Ireland Vilnius, Lithuania Zaragoza, Spain
Sustainable Mobility	Mobility labs were created to develop context-specific solutions for sustainable school commuting.	Kaunas, Lithuania Sofia, Bulgaria Braga, Portugal Galway, Ireland
Sustainable Food	Underlying narratives of food system innovations were explored through knowledge exchange events with changemakers.	Stockholm, Sweden Cella Monte, Italy Wageningen, Netherlands Košice, Slovakia
Preserving Biodiversity	Study circles were established to facilitate informal adult learning around local biodiversity.	Tolmin, Slovenia Kilfinane, Ireland Stockholm, Sweden Athens, Greece

However, we are aware that the interventions undertaken as part of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project and the insights developed are situated within the contexts of the interventions, with this influencing the discourse we were exposed to. Interventions were coordinated by institutions whose strategies align with the ambitions of the EU Green Deal, and were situated within the overarching framework of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments funding programme. Consequently, our understandings of the experiences associated with working towards a sustainable Europe are confined to particular organisations, perspectives, and contexts. As such, there was a value (and arguably a need) to expose ourselves to wider discourse around the EU Green Deal topics and approaches towards achieving a sustainable future. Embracing wider discourse also supports the identification of conclusions that are relevant for those countries where social experiments did not take place.

1.2. Using social listening to capture wider discourse on sustainability topics

A Social Listening approach was adopted to engage with wider discourse around Green Deal topics. Social listening refers to the process of monitoring and analysing conversations, trends, and sentiments expressed across social media platforms and other online spaces (Parks et al., 2024). The ability to identify these emerging trends, emotional responses, and thematic clusters in real time or retrospectively through the analysis of informal, user-generated content such as social media posts, comments, hashtags, and shared articles (McGowan, 2022) is how Social Listening differs from traditional media monitoring, which tracks formal news coverage. The Meltwater platform was used to conduct the social listening. By using social listening, we were able to examine how citizens engage with the themes addressed through the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams and the cross-cutting themes of the overall project. Specifically, we were able to explore how themes connected to the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments were resonating with ordinary citizens in informal online spaces across the European Union. Doing this enabled us to develop a greater understanding of the scale, generalisability, and international comparability of the governance, policy, and regulatory recommendations that were developed based upon experiences throughout the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.

An iterative approach was taken to develop the search terms used in the Meltwater search, to ensure they captured data relevant to the core focus of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. The search terms were refined over time and in consultation with the various SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium partners involved with each of the experiment streams. Through this process, we found there to be a fine line between search terms too specific to capture results and search terms too generic that the results were of less relevance to the foci of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams.

The recommendations generated based upon the experiment stream activities provided the foundation for the search terms. Whilst it was not possible to use social listening to capture citizen perspectives on the specifics of the recommendations generated based upon the SHARED GREEN DEAL project we were able to use social listening to capture the tone of online conversations surrounding the general topic areas within which these policy recommendations sit. In doing so, we were able to develop a rich, detailed picture of the information environment in which these recommendations and associated (policy) actions would be situated.

The Meltwater data captured informal, organic conversations taking place across social media platforms, blogs, forums, and digital news outlets related to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment streams in 10 European languages. Searches were undertaken in Croatian, Czech, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Latvian, Romanian, and Spanish – chosen in part to capture locations where the SHARED GREEN DEAL project had not run in-person initiatives (Table 2). Although the searches were undertaken in these 10 languages, the Meltwater search also captured online discourse in other, additional languages that shared common phrases and terms, and these are also included in our analysis.

A quantitative summary of these search results was produced by the Meltwater platform, including total mentions, total reach, and social echo¹. Sentiment analysis², key phrase frequency, and

1 Social echo refers to the amplification and reinforcement of specific messages when they are shared online. It relates to the visibility of these messages through repeated sharing across networks, reaching audiences beyond those of the original source.

2 Sentiment analysis captures the emotional tone of the online discourse, with content classified as positive, negative, or neutral.

the geographical spread of outputs were also produced. The data and summaries produced by Meltwater provided a starting point for further analysis undertaken by SHARED GREEN DEAL researchers. Following a period of data familiarisation, researchers used the sentiment analysis results, the key topic frequency, and the topics associated with heightened engagement and emotion to identify key topics. These key topics are a snapshot of the issues, language, framing, phraseology and controversies related to the SHARED GREEN DEAL's broad areas of inquiry. Links between these key topics and broader contextual factors that may influence the social discourse (e.g. policy debates, national events etc.) were also identified by researchers. Further details on the methodology can be found in the Appendix to this report (Martin et al., 2026).

Table 2: A breakdown of the languages included within the social listening analysis, and the justification for their inclusion

Language	Justification for inclusion in social listening
English, French, Spanish	One of the most commonly spoken languages in Europe, with both native and second-language speakers.
German	One of the most commonly spoken languages in Europe, with both native and second-language speakers. There was not a SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment conducted in the language, so the social listening exercise gave insight into how sustainability topics were being discussed by German speakers.
Croatian, Czech, Estonian, Finnish, Latvian, Romanian	There were no SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments conducted in these languages, so the social listening exercise gave insight into how sustainability topics were being discussed by those who speak these languages.

Whilst the Meltwater analysis provided insight into the online discourse around the Green Deal topics explored within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, the nature of the search terms used and the breadth of online materials meant that some of the data retrieved were less closely related to these topics. For example, there are instances where the nicknames of sports teams resulted in their inclusion, such as online discourse about Brentford Football Club who are known as 'The Bees' being included in the Preserving Biodiversity Meltwater data.

However, the intention behind the Meltwater analysis was to capture different types of discourse that the SHARED GREEN DEAL project had not been exposed to. Indeed, despite the importance of these alternative types of discourse, they are often overlooked within research and policy spaces. Thus, there was not the expectation, nor the requirement for the Meltwater analysis to be representative or perfectly comprehensive. These limitations of the approach are highlighted to support transparency in the research process, and efforts have been made to mitigate the impact of the less relevant online discourse through the analysis undertaken by the SHARED GREEN DEAL researchers (as outlined in the Methodological Appendix, see Martin et al., 2026).

1.3. The aim and structure of this report

This report is for policyworkers, practitioners and anyone interested in the social narratives around key sustainability topics. Through the analysis undertaken, we have been exposed to different dialogues related to EU Green Deal topics. Thus, our hope is that the analysis conducted can inform how these topics are presented, addressed, and discussed within policy going forwards.

Insights and key themes from the social listening searches related to each of the six experiment streams (Clean Energy; Circular Economy; Efficient Renovations; Sustainable Mobility; Sustainable Food; Preserving Biodiversity) are presented in turn, before reflecting on the five cross-cutting themes (Gender and Diversity; Geographic and Institutional Differences; Governance Agendas; Justice, Vulnerability and Inequality; Societal Challenges) of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. Each of these sections follows the same structure: firstly, we summarise the focus of the experiment stream/cross-cutting theme and the search terms used, we then detail the key themes identified, and close with reflections on how these key topics relate to the learnings from the SHARED GREEN DEAL project activities. When discussing the themes identified through the social listening, we include specific quotes from the social listening dataset to help illustrate the points being made. These quotes have been translated into English by the research team using Google Translate. Following these thematically focused sections, we reflect on the policy implications of the analysis undertaken.

2. Efficient Renovations

Highlights

- Practical information related to renovation practices and funding initiatives are shared via online spaces and networks.
- The opportunities for renovation practices to support vulnerable groups in society – including those vulnerable to energy poverty and those with disabilities – are discussed within online discourse.
- Legislative and institutional expectations around renovation practices were highlighted as a prompt for renovation activity across Europe.

window replacements natural building materials
 clay plaster tiny homes co-housing
 lime-based paints **DIY renovation**
 government subsidies low-VOC finishes Retrofitting
solar panels on farmhouses Hempcrete
 recycled heat pump installation modular construction
 wood **insulation upgrades** energy efficiency
 rural restoration **non-toxic insulation**

Figure 2a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 2b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 2c. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords³

3 Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “roku” [year], and therefore are not shown.

2.1. Introducing the Efficient Renovations stream

The renovations experiment stream focused on bringing together citizens and professionals to share know-how on renovation i.e. practical experience-based knowledge. These ‘Knowledge Networks’ focused on domestic retrofit, with a key component of the experiment stream being the organisation of eco-tours to pre- and post-renovation homes to support experiential learning. Further details on the Efficient Renovations experiment activities can be found in the [“Bringing together citizens and professionals to develop know-how for energy efficient renovations”](#) report (Foulds et al., 2025).

The Knowledge Networks were found to facilitate sustained interactions between professionals and citizens. A particular strength of this approach was that it provided actionable, up-to-date, place-specific information about renovation processes, with this information being supported by the sharing of know-how from those with lived experience of renovation. The Knowledge Networks organised through the SHARED GREEN DEAL project have had a Multiplier effect for renovation action as a result of flexible and evolving connections. Key policy recommendations from the Efficient Renovations experiment stream include working with established community partners and gatekeepers, engaging with renovation knowledge from different sources, organising in-person eco-tours to renovation sites, and providing information in accessible ways through one-stop-shops.

The Meltwater search terms were informed by the topics covered in the Efficient Renovations experiment stream. Specifically, the search terms (Figure 2a) focused on “DIY Renovation Culture”, “Energy Efficiency”, and “Natural Materials and Health” (see the Methodological Appendix for example search strings).

2.2. Key topics identified through social listening

2.2.1. Overview

Throughout 2024, renovation-related content generated approximately 518,000 mentions, showing a slight decline of 1.9% compared to the previous year. Despite this, the potential reach increased by 3.7% and the visibility of renovation topics grew.

Sentiment analysis reveals that the majority of mentions were neutral (83%), with positive sentiment accounting for 15% and negative sentiment just 2.9%. The distinct lack of negative sentiment is perhaps an indication that this is an area relatively free of political polarisation.

Keywords (Figure 2c) such as “energy efficiency”, “reabilitare” [rehabilitation], “rekonstrukce” [renovation], and “korun” [Czech currency] dominated the discourse, highlighting the intersection of renovations with climate goals, household economics, and regional policy initiatives. The frequent use of terms related to financial investment and project timelines suggests that affordability and feasibility are central concerns in renovation discussions.

Geographically, France was the country with the most online posts related to efficient renovations, with 21.9% of total, followed by Germany 20.2%, Spain 15.7%, the United Kingdom 11.3%, and Romania 7.3%⁴ (Figure 2b). A contributing factors to France’s prominence may have been due to discussions about national energy transition strategies and public debates around housing standards.

⁴ As a reminder, the languages searched were Croatian, Czech, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Latvian, Romanian, and Spanish.

2.2.2. Sharing knowledge through online spaces and networks

Online spaces provided a platform for individuals to share their experiences of renovation processes and to ask for specific support. A range of information is shared to support others in their renovation process via one-way posts, from general tips and tricks (e.g. “While tried and tested tips like bleeding radiators will aid energy efficiency, there are other quick fixes you can implement to keep...” [English, Online News, Energy Efficiency]) to contextually-situated recommendations (e.g. a newsletter, translated to “Your tailored energy”, which provides up-to-date advice based upon the current market conditions [French, Blog, Natural Materials and Health]).

More discursive interactions around energy efficiency and learning occur via forums, with there being multiple examples of forum entries where someone has asked for advice around a particular technology or renovation activity. Responses to these queries include sharing personal experiences, as well as directing the enquirer to other sources of information, as shown in this example translated from German: “since I insulated the reveals of the terrace doors with it, I preferred that. Whether the manufacturers are fundamentally different I cannot say, but I almost don’t think so. At Claytec you can also find some information and videos about interior insulation / wall heating / clay plaster.” [German, Forum, Natural Materials and Health].

In-person activities to support learning were also referenced within the social listening responses – with these learning opportunities relating to both professional and citizen groups. For example, a French company that works on renovations reflected on how being involved with a professional network enabled them to attend events where they “exchange with the other members, we inspire each other, we leave boosted. There is a real spirit of solidarity and mutual aid between members” [French, Online, Energy Efficiency]. A Spanish media report outlines an upcoming “training activity, which will allow citizens to become aware in a fun and entertaining way about the need to adopt habits that contribute to favouring the environment and about the fight against the climate emergency” [Spanish, Online News, Energy Efficiency]. The diverse range of activities organised demonstrates different opportunities and mechanisms available to individuals that wish to learn how to address climate change, including through renovation practices.

Retrofitting older structures to meet new EU energy standards was a theme across the Meltwater responses, with users sharing their experiences installing insulation, replacing windows, and integrating heat pumps. Reference was made to the variety of initiatives available to support renovation processes, for example, a news article which outlined how “you might be able to apply for support with the cost of energy efficiency upgrades like insulation, a new boiler or a heat pump” [English, Online News, Energy Efficiency].

2.2.3. Social benefits of renovation

Across the social listening data, renovation practices were highlighted that support vulnerable groups in society – including those vulnerable to energy poverty and those with disabilities. Often, the posts highlighting the social benefits were not from those experiencing the targeted social benefits, rather those who are contributing to the achievement of, or simply observing, the generation of these benefits.

The opportunity for renovation practices, in particular those related to improving energy efficiency to address fuel poverty is highlighted through the social listening data, for example “poor energy efficiency remains one of the main drivers of fuel poverty” [English, Online News, Energy Efficiency]. Many of these posts relate to coordinated efforts to address fuel poverty through coordinated action, for example within the UK where “Buckinghamshire Council secured £1.04 million

to retrofit 48 homes, improving energy efficiency and reducing fuel poverty” [English, Online News, Energy Efficiency].

Within Italy⁵, the Dopo di Noi scheme has contributed to coverage of buildings being renovated to provide a space for those with disabilities. These renovated spaces include converting a building to become a dedicated training space for individuals that will “offer a social assistance service for paths oriented towards teaching, professional training, support of acquired autonomy, preferably, although not exclusively, job placement” [Italian, Online News, DIY Renovation Culture], or the renovation of buildings into social cohousing for children with disabilities [Italian, Online News, DIY Renovation Culture]. The development of renovation activities that intentionally provide social impact highlights how renovation practices are not motivated solely by technical and economic factors.

However, despite positive sentiments towards community groups receiving funding for energy-saving improvements, there were also negative mentions related to these processes including rising energy prices and the bureaucratic hurdles involved in accessing subsidies.

2.3. Linking the social listening analysis to the Efficient Renovations social experiments

When looking across the social listening data, and the key topics identified in the Meltwater automated analysis and those identified by the SHARED GREEN DEAL researchers, there are multiple links to the SHARED GREEN DEAL Efficient Renovations social experiments. These links relate not only to the topics covered within the experiment stream, but also the underlying mechanisms of the local interventions themselves.

The presence of online and in-person activities to share tips and learning related to renovation processes demonstrates how the public are engaging with information sources related to renovation. This aligns with insights from the local interventions where we found that individuals really valued having a reliable, consistent information source on these key issues. The value of lived experience across the social listening data, shown through the use of forums focused on renovation, also aligns with our experiences within the local interventions, particularly the eco-tours and the positive responses to being able to learn from those who had already undertaken domestic retrofit activities.

Related to this, the availability of alternative sources of diverse knowledge was a key component of the Knowledge Networks developed as part of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments. The variety of voices and perspectives on renovation that people are able to access online and discuss and support highlights the value of engaging with knowledge beyond formal institutions.

Finally, the supportive space of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment programme and the associated funding was considered by the local partners as a critical mechanism for undertaking activities and supporting local renovation processes. As shown through the social listening data, challenges related to accessing funding are prevalent across Europe. Throughout the social experiments, discussions on where to access funding and the provision of support to overcome bureaucratic hurdles were considered particularly helpful to Knowledge Network members. With similar questions, and support, have been shown to exist through the social listening results.

⁵ Whilst Italian was not one of the 10 languages used for the Social Listening searches, Meltwater captured relevant Italian social discourse related to the Efficient Renovations theme as there are common phrases across Italian and the languages searched.

3. Clean Energy

Highlights

- The potential for renewable energy technologies to support European and national energy independence is a popular topic within online discourse.
- Existing funding schemes to support the development of renewable energy technologies is praised, but there is a strong sentiment that further, and more diverse, support is required to achieve sustainability ambitions.
- The politics of energy, in particular tensions related to the raw materials of renewable energy technologies, the impact of geopolitical crises, and the workings of national governments, is recognised by European citizens.

Figure 3a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 3b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 3c. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords⁶

6 Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “party”, and therefore are not shown.

3.1. Introducing the Clean Energy experiment stream

The clean energy experiment stream focused on co-creating shared visions of desirable energy futures across the experiment locations. These visions were developed during workshops with government representatives, businesses and residents. Further detail on the experiment activities are presented in the “[Community visioning for just, clean energy futures in Europe](#)” report (Gray et al., 2025a).

Through these workshops, participants were able to network and participate in capacity building activities. The use of community visioning was found to support wider engagement in just, clean energy transitions, including catalysing collective action around the issue. Key policy recommendations from the Clean Energy experiment stream include scaling interventions at the community level to support participation in energy decision-making, establishing effective communication with key stakeholders to understand their priorities and contexts, collaborating across different government departments, and supporting community activities and NGO activities, in particular through the provision of funding.

The topics covered by the Clean Energy experiment stream informed the search terms (Figure 3a) used for the Meltwater social listening activity. Specifically, searches focused on “Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety”, “Scepticism and Misinformation”.

3.2. Key topics identified through social listening

3.2.1. Overview

The social listening data highlighted a 7% increase in mentions of clean energy in 2024 compared to the previous year, with around 41,800 mentions online. Visibility grew even faster, with potential reach rising by 17% to 66.7 billion impressions. This indicates that clean energy is attracting greater attention in mainstream and high-profile media, likely driven by policy announcements, public debate, and wider energy security concerns.

Based upon Meltwater’s sentiment analysis, most of the discussions around clean energy were neutral in tone (80%), with 15% having a positive sentiment and less than 5% having a negative sentiment. Positive coverage was most closely linked to energy independence, affordability, and renewable energy, while negative sentiment clustered around energy bills and scepticism about the cost or delivery of clean energy initiatives.

Common keywords (Figure 3c) such as “energy independence,” “home,” “energy security,” and “bills” show that clean energy is widely understood through the lens of household costs, national policy, and economic stability, as much as environmental benefit.

National policy contexts informed the discussion around this topic, for example balcony solar panels (Balkonkraftwerke) in Germany, energy sobriety (sobriété énergétique) in France, self-consumption (autoconsumo) and selling excess solar power back to the grid in Spain, and Italy’s Superbonus 110% scheme for home energy upgrades were frequently mentioned (Figure 3b).

Overall, the findings suggest that clean energy is highly visible and broadly supported, but engagement depends heavily on clear links to household affordability, national security, and tangible policy benefits.

3.2.2. Energy independence through renewable energy

The analysis of the Meltwater data highlighted perceptions that the expansion of renewable energy technologies is a critical mechanism for achieving energy independence. This was discussed in reference to a number of European countries, including the UK, France, Germany, and Denmark.

As well as broadly supporting energy independence, the environmental co-benefits of addressing climate change were also highlighted within the online discourse, as shown in an online news article discussing, “producing your own electricity, aiming for energy independence, and doing so in an eco-responsible way” [French, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety]. As well as a forum post on solar energy, reflecting how “Innovative and highly efficient technology is the key to reducing emissions and accelerating energy independence in Europe” [German, Forum, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety].

The benefits of expanding renewable energy to support energy independence were not discussed solely at the national or European scale, rather discussions related to the opportunities for local communities were also captured in the social listening. For example, a news article outlined how offshore wind turbines were “making a tangible impact on Denmark’s energy independence while benefiting the local community” [English, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety]. Similarly, in Spain the specific benefits of renewable energy for the Irrigation community were highlighted [Spanish, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety].

3.2.3. The role of funding

A central community benefit related to clean energy, and renewable energy projects more specifically, related to the potential monetary savings. As shown in the case of Spain, “self-consumption allows energy independence and reduces the electricity bill” [Spanish, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety] and “the use of photovoltaic energy offers a solution for energy independence for both homes and businesses” [Spanish, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety]. Within this, it highlights the multiple scales at which renewable energy projects can have impacts, with these impacts extending beyond environmental to include economic and social impacts.

However, the importance of funding to be able to develop the renewable energy communities required to achieve these benefits cannot be understated. Within the Meltwater data, multiple references are made to the “attractive subsidies and financing options available” [German, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety] and “flexible financing models” [German, Online News, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety]. However, as shown in a Finnish forum post, these positive framings of funding available are not universal, “in handling the energy crisis, the National Coalition Party demands significantly larger subsidies from the state”. [Finnish, Forum, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety].

3.2.4. Energy as a political issue

The political nature of energy was evident within the social listening data. The politics of energy related to the raw materials required for renewable energy technologies, the impact of geopolitical crises, and the workings of national governments.

Regarding the raw materials required for renewable energy technologies, Lithium mining was a highly discussed topic within the social listening data. For example, “Lithium mining in the

Czech Republic is more of a political topic today” [Czech, Online News, Energy Scepticism and Misinformation] and “Lithium mining isn’t hreat neither [sic]... Climate change so is already ruining everything and everyones lives [sic]” [English, Forum, Energy Scepticism and Misinformation]. However, there was also discourse around the activities being undertaken to address these challenges, including “a company from Grenoble will show how to minimise the impact of solar panels by reusing raw materials” [French, Online News, Energy Scepticism and Misinformation].

The impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on energy discourse was captured through the social listening, including reflections on how the associated energy crisis was a catalyst for action towards energy independence: “My optimism mainly stems from the fact that, since the Russian invasion of Ukraine, European countries have begun to truly see the value of energy independence. For most, renewables are the only path to achieve it, therefore transitioning to renewables isn’t just about climate” [English, Comment, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety].

There was also scepticism shared around the coordination of energy projects, and the power dynamics in play, as shown through a French comment in which the “contracts being sold to friends” [French, Comment, Energy Independence and Climate Anxiety] was mentioned.

3.3. Linking the social listening analysis to the Clean Energy social experiments

The social listening insights related to clean energy resonate with the findings and recommendations of the SHARED GREEN DEAL Clean Energy experiments. The opportunities for community participation in clean energy activities, and the associated benefits of the involvement of different stakeholders is evident both within online discourse and the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. Experiences from the SHARED GREEN DEAL project highlighted the importance of accessible funding to undertake activities that address challenges of clean energy, with one of the recommendations focusing on ensuring the provision of funding for local energy activities. The centrality of funding for undertaking local, climate-related activities was shown through the social listening activity.

Both the social listening activities and the experiences of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project highlight the importance of communication across different stakeholders within the energy space. The inherently political nature of energy demonstrates the complex relationships that underpin these energy-related activities and the need to navigate different power dynamics to achieve a sustainable, equitable energy future.

The role of cross-scalar collaborations, particularly collaborations between different scales of government, was highlighted within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project and the online discourse. Through these collaborations, activities to support the growth of clean energy practices can be supported and progress towards a more sustainable society achieved.

4. Circular Economy

Highlights

- There is an awareness of the different sectors in which circular economy principles can be adopted, as well as the impact of these actions on both individuals and society more broadly.
- A variety of initiatives – from in-person awareness raising activities to supportive infrastructures for circular economy practices – are discussed within online dialogues.
- Personal experiences of engaging with circular economy practices are valued within the online space.

Figure 4a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 4b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 4c. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords⁷

⁷ Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “little bit”, and therefore are not shown.

4.1. Introducing the Circular Economy experiment stream

The Circular Economy experiment stream established Local Accelerator Hubs to support local businesses to implement circular economy practices. Through group meetings, businesses were introduced to the concept of circular economy and provided the space to consider how they could adopt circular economy practices and provided support to do so. Further details on the experiment activities can be found in the [“Implementing Local Accelerator Hubs to foster business innovation in the circular economy”](#) report (Ruiz et al., 2025).

The Local Accelerator Hubs were an interactive space for knowledge sharing and collaboration, with these activities supporting the establishment of a robust business ecosystem for circular economy practices. Based upon the experiences of the SHARED GREEN DEAL Circular Economy experiments, the following recommendations were developed: strengthen collaboration and innovation through local accelerator hubs, invest in skills development and digital knowledge platforms, strengthen and harmonise regulatory/financial frameworks for circular economy innovations, and facilitate multi-stakeholder engagement and cross-sectoral collaborations.

The topics covered in the Circular Economy experiment stream were used to develop the search terms used for the Meltwater social listening activity (Figure 4a). Specifically, searches focused on “Recycling and Reducing”, “Upcycling and DIY Culture” and alternative circular economy approaches, collectively termed “Why Don’t We Do This More Moments”.

4.2. Key topics identified through social listening

4.2.1. Overview

Public engagement on the topic of circularity has increased. In 2024, measures of sharing and interaction rose by 68%, reaching 79.2 million engagements, suggesting that circularity topics are resonating more strongly with audiences and prompting more active discussion and amplification.

Most coverage was neutral in tone (82%), indicating that circularity is generally presented as practical and solution-focused, rather than contentious. Positive sentiment was closely linked to upcycling, sustainable lifestyles, and DIY practices, while negative sentiment tended to arise around waste management challenges and systemic inefficiencies (Figure 4c).

Economic factors featured prominently in the discussion. Frequent references to second-hand goods, costs, prices, and investment levels suggest that circularity is widely understood through a financial lens, highlighting both potential savings for consumers.

Geographically, Germany dominated the conversation, accounting for 40.6% of mentions (477,000), followed by the United Kingdom (21.2%), Spain (8.0%), Ireland (5.0%), and France (4.5%) (Figure 4b). Germany’s prominence likely reflects its well-established recycling systems and strong media focus on sustainability initiatives.

Highly shared editorial content focused on sustainable festivals, new recycling infrastructure, and EU policy announcements. Stories that combined practical innovation with broader environmental goals were particularly effective in driving public interest and engagement.

4.2.2. The diversity and benefits of circular economy practices

Across the social listening data, addressing food waste was a dominant entry point for engaging with circular economy principles. With many statistics shared about the extent to which this is an ongoing challenge, for example, “Households unnecessarily threw away the equivalent of one billion meals every day worldwide in 2022, according to UN estimates” [French, Online News, Why Don't We Do This More Moments]. Although, promotional materials highlighting the adoption of circular economy across non-food sectors demonstrated the diversity of ways in which circular economy is being engaged with. As shown through a chemical engineering company outlined how they are committed to plastic upcycling [Italian, Online News, Upcycling and DIY culture].

The benefits of adopting circular economy practices were highlighted within the data, with economic arguments dominating – “a small change makes a big difference. Reducing food waste not only benefits your wallet” [French, TV Broadcast, Why Don't We Do This More Moments] and “I buy second-hand mainly because it is cheap” [Swedish, comment, recycling]. Through this, it highlights the cost-saving opportunities associated with circular economy practices.

4.2.3. Initiatives to support circular economy practices

As well as providing details on current engagement with circular economy principles, the social listening data also highlighted dialogues around initiatives to support others to engage with these principles. Initiatives ranged from in-person activities to raise awareness of circular economy such as the “International Recycling Tour” which includes “a bold visual statement through installations” and “calls on everyone to #Re:Generate” [Polish, Forum, Recycling and Reducing] to food preparation kits to help reduce food waste where “each box contains the right quantities” [French, Online News, Why Don't We Do This More Moments]. The environmental impact of the fashion industry and means for addressing this were also captured within the social listening data, including reflections that “the new message is about recycling, upcycling, vintage and shopping in a more thoughtful way” [French, Online News, Upcycling and DIY Culture].

Forums were shown to be an important space for circular economy practices – both by being a space where individuals can access goods second hand and a space where individuals can access knowledge and support from others engaging in these practices. Product listings for second hand goods were captured across a range of products, from technology to clothing, often accompanied by a high-level of detail about the product – for example, a post selling a second-hand car detailed the full specification and maintenance history [German, Forum, Recycling and Reducing]. The knowledge and support provided through forums on undertaking circular economy practices were also highly detailed, often drawing upon the personal experiences of the individual sharing the knowledge, for example, “Regarding the ACC: Have you activated the main switch? Sounds silly, but I once had it turned off and it took me a while to reactivate it with the main switch” [German, Forum, Recycling and Reducing]. The social media platform TikTok was also identified as a useful resource for engaging with circular economy principles, “I searched reducing food waste on TikTok and found loads of videos on there” [UK, Radio Broadcast, Why Don't We Do This More Moments].

4.3. Linking the social listening analysis to the Circular Economy experiment stream

Considering the insights obtained through the social listening activity and the learnings from the Circular Economy experiment stream, the centrality of skills and knowledge to engaging with circular economy practices is commonly referenced. The insights highlight how there are multiple sources where this information can come from – including through online spaces such as forums, in-person events, and personal networks. There are also a diverse range of activities developed to support engagement with circularity, for example, the Local Accelerator Hubs developed as part of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.

The cross-sectoral nature of circular economy highlights the importance of involving stakeholders from different sectors within discussions. These interactions can advance progress towards a more circular society in an effective and efficient way. The engagement, and alignment, of different sectors supports the establishment of a shared culture of circularity.

5. Promoting Biodiversity

Highlights

- Online discourse about biodiversity across Europe often focuses on interactions that individuals have with particular spaces and issues.
- The benefits of biodiversity are recognised across European voices.
- Events and campaigns are highlighted as important mechanisms for raising awareness of biodiversity and engaging individuals in activities.
- Existing institutional support for biodiversity initiatives are referenced within the online space. There are also comments on where further institutional support and interventions are required.

Figure 5a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 5b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 5c. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords⁸

⁸ Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “children”, and therefore are not shown.

5.1. Introducing the Promoting Biodiversity experiment stream

The Promoting Biodiversity experiment stream facilitated informal adult learning around biodiversity by establishing local study circles. Study circles are a non-formal learning approach, with the SHARED GREEN DEAL study circles being designed to help reconnect citizens with nature. Further details on the experiment activities can be found in the [“Exploring the Study Circle approach in fostering change in biodiversity values among adults”](#) report (Šmid Hribar et al., 2025).

By bringing together adults interested in biodiversity and enabling them to determine the area of biodiversity they were most interested in learning about, it provided the space for community-based learning and supported positive behaviour change. Drawing upon learnings and experiences from the experiment stream’s activities, the following recommendations were developed: utilise study circles to advance knowledge and awareness of biodiversity, strengthen citizen participation for biodiversity preservation, encourage individual engagement in biodiversity initiatives to support collective preservation efforts, and implement capacity building programmes to equip communities to participate in biodiversity initiatives.

The topics covered within the Promoting Biodiversity experiment stream were used to develop the search terms used for the Meltwater social listening activity (Figure 5a). Specifically, searches focused on “Grieving for Nature Loss”, “Impact on Daily Lives”, and “Waste and Pollution”.

5.2. Key topics identified through social listening

5.2.1. Overview

Biodiversity was mentioned around 454,000 times online, representing a 7.9% decrease compared with the previous year. However, the potential reach of these mentions increased by 4.4%, reaching an estimated 906 billion impressions.

The most discussed biodiversity content was emotionally charged, particularly where biodiversity loss was linked to habitat destruction, species extinction, and threats to green spaces. Most biodiversity coverage was neutral in tone (78%), with 13% positive and 8.8% negative sentiment. This suggests that discussion is largely informational rather than opinion-driven.

Emotionally resonant discussions frequently connected biodiversity to human wellbeing, especially through themes such as “home,” and “mental health” (Figure 5c). This points to a growing public narrative that frames biodiversity not only as an environmental issue, but as one that directly affects quality of life, public health, and community resilience, particularly in urban settings.

The United Kingdom accounted for 30.9% of all mentions, followed by Germany (28%) and France (12.7%), with Spain and Austria also contributing significantly. Mentions were slightly more likely to be led by men (31.7k) than women (24.4k), with a smaller share of mixed-gender discussions (8.6k) (Figure 5b).

Public attention to biodiversity is increasingly shaped by institutional action and governance debates, and biodiversity is being discussed alongside wider climate, regulatory, and digital policy issues. The most widely shared editorial content focused on EU policy decisions, environmental

legal action, and emissions-related initiatives. High-engagement stories included EU infringement procedures, state aid for emissions reduction, and regulation of digital platforms.

5.2.2. Awareness of the positive dimensions of biodiversity

The social listening analysis highlighted that rather than using the term biodiversity within citizen dialogue, other phrases were used to capture biodiversity including “nature”, “species”, “wildlife” and “environment”. With this highlighting that there is an engagement with biodiversity across Europe, but that it is often referred to in relation to the interactions that individuals have with particular spaces and issues.

The data highlights that there is a general awareness of the positive impacts that biodiversity has on individuals, with this predominantly being discussed in relation to accessing green space - “The creation of these green spaces is essential to improve quality of life and promote a healthy lifestyle.” [Spanish, online news, impact]. A specific example of this was outlined in a news article where a hospital has created a green space based to support the health and wellbeing of patients [English, Online News, Impact on Daily Lives].

5.2.3. Events to raise awareness

Whilst a general awareness of the benefits of biodiversity was shown through the social listening data, the data also highlighted a number of events being organised to raise awareness of biodiversity issues, as well as support individuals to engage more with biodiversity. These events ranged from being supportive spaces to think about and interact with biodiversity, such as individuals writing down ideas that could raise awareness of bees [German, Online News, Impact on Daily Lives], to events that have a more tangential link to biodiversity, for example a singer hosted a Christmas concert to raise money for a charity that champions access and engagement with green spaces [English, Online News, Impact on Daily Lives].

The data also highlighted how there is an awareness of the role that individuals play in supporting biodiversity actions - “we can contribute to the preservation of this endangered species [hedgehogs]” [Croatian, Online News, Grieving for Nature Loss]. The discussion around endangered species was particularly strong in Germany, where there were articles related to invasive species [German, Online News, Grieving for Nature Loss] and the “fights against species extinction” [German, Online News, Grieving for Nature Loss]. Awareness raising events can support the engagement of others with the required behaviours. the value of these events to further raise awareness and have others engage in these behaviours.

5.2.4. Institutional support for biodiversity

Alongside discussions around the role of individuals in preserving biodiversity, online narratives also cover the role of institutions in supporting actions. The institutional support highlighted ranges from treaties designed to protect the environment, such as the “global high seas protection agreement [which] safeguards endangered species and habitats beyond national borders” [German, Online News, Grieving for Nature Loss] and the “Nature Conservation Act” in Czechia [Czech, Online News, Grieving for Nature Loss]. However, the discussions around the Czech Nature Conservation Act highlight the complex governance of biodiversity actions, with the general sentiment being positive but concerns highlighted over some of the framing.

The establishment of ‘guardians’ for endangered species is also highlighted as a useful mechanism for preserving biodiversity. In Croatia, “nature guardians can quickly identify and track endangered species, aiding in strategic conservation measures” [Croatian, Online News, Grieving for Nature Loss] with this not only highlighting the value of a situated approach to conservation activities, but also the value of having centrally organised activities. Similarly, zoos are discussed as important spaces for supporting endangered species, and thus, biodiversity more broadly. Zoos can “form a gene bank aimed at preventing the extinction of certain species. When animals are crossbred between zoos, they can be released into the wild to reproduce.” [Finnish, Forum, Grieving for Nature Loss].

5.3. Linking the social listening analysis to the Preserving Biodiversity experiment stream

Both the social listening data and the experiences of the Preserving Biodiversity experiment stream highlight the importance of raising awareness about biodiversity, with multiple mechanisms established to support this. By raising awareness of the need to address different biodiversity challenges, it supports individual engagement with and mobilisation around these challenges. In particular, situating discussions around biodiversity within local contexts and aligning with topics of interest to the local public (as was the case with the SHARED GREEN DEAL study circles) is particularly effective at encouraging engagement.

Yet, individual actions are not enough. Rather there is a need for collective action to have the level of impact required to have a sustained shift in practices that support the preservation of biodiversity. Collective action around biodiversity is supported by the engagement of institutional actors around the issue, and the establishment of more formalised mechanisms to support change.

6. Sustainable Food

Highlights

- Different practices to support a shift to a more sustainable food system are present within online discourse. These practices transcend different scales and include various actors from producers to consumers.
- Environmental factors that act as a barrier to the achievement of a sustainable food system are referenced by European citizens.
- The socio-economic elements of a sustainable food system are highlighted and discussed within the online space, bringing attention to the need for a joined-up approach to achieving sustainability ambitions.

Figure 6a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 6b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)⁹

6.1. Introducing the Sustainable Food experiment stream

The Sustainable Food experiment stream organised knowledge exchange events with change-makers associated with the food system. These knowledge exchange events took the form of a Transition Arena, whereby narratives of food system innovations were explored in a coordinated way. Further details on the experiment activities can be found in the “[Scaling food systems transitions](#)” report (Beers et al., 2025).

By bringing together food system changemakers, the experiment stream was able to find pathways to more sustainable and just food systems. The pathways that were developed considered both systemic challenges and potential local actions. Based upon the experiences and reflections from the Transition Arena activities, the following recommendations were developed: learn from local experiences, particularly to understand institutional barriers; strengthen coordination across local initiatives; invest in market conditions that favour local producers; and, address structural barriers to healthy and sustainable food choices.

⁹ Due to food being a broad topic, the key words included within the sentiment analysis were not relevant to the SHARED GREEN DEAL topic or the analysis undertaken so we have not presented the sentiment analysis.

As with the other experiment streams, the topics covered within the Sustainable Food experiment stream informed the search terms used for the Meltwater social listening activity (Figure 5a). Specifically, searches focused on “Cost of Living and Home Cooking”, “Farming and Agriculture”, and “Sustainability and Ethics”.

6.2. Key topics identified through social listening

6.2.1. Overview

Food-related content generated approximately 455,000 mentions in 2024 – a 15% decrease compared to the previous year. Despite this drop in volume, the potential reach remained high at 1.24 trillion impressions, though it also declined by 13.7%.

Sentiment analysis shows that the majority of mentions were neutral (76%), with negative sentiment accounting for 14% and positive sentiment 9.4%. This notable negativity, arises around issues such as affordability, ethical sourcing, and climate impacts on agriculture. The presence of emotionally charged language such as sadness, anger, and fear underscores the depth of public concern around food security and sustainability.

Key topics related to food included the health risks of ultra-processed foods, climate-related disruptions to agriculture (such as El Niño), and global water scarcity. These issues were frequently linked to broader environmental and geopolitical narratives, including humanitarian aid, climate resilience, and EU agricultural policy reform.

Geographically, Spain led the conversation with 107,000 mentions (23.6% of total), followed by Germany (18%), the United Kingdom (17.8%), France (11.3%), and Poland (9.6%) (Figure 5b). Spain's prominence may be linked to localised droughts and political debates around food systems.

6.2.2. Sustainable food practices

The social listening data highlights online discourse around ways in which food practices can be made more sustainable. The online discourse engages with sustainable food practices from the growing to the consumption stage.

Regarding sustainable farming practices, opportunities for regenerative agriculture are presented online. As covered in a French TV broadcast, farmers are “implementing regenerative soil agriculture, also called soil conservation” [French, TV Broadcast, Sustainability and Ethics]. With the shift to more sustainable farming practices being supported by the “optimisation of industrial tools” [French, Online News, Sustainability and Ethics] with this highlighting the socio-technical nature of sustainability transitions.

Online, there is an awareness of the benefits that a plant-based diet can provide, both for the environment and on an individual's health – “vegan food is increasingly recognised as the food of the future. Plant-based nutrition offers sustainable solutions not only for human health but also for the preservation of our planet” [Croatian, Online News, Sustainability and Ethics]. From an environmental sustainability perspective, much of the data captures the impact of a vegan diet, as shown in a German news article, “a plant-based diet is considered the lowest-emission option for the planet” [German, Online News, Sustainability and Ethics].

The merits of a plant-based diet also brought into conversation with ongoing debates related to ultra-processed food, with there being increasing “consumer pushback against heavily processed foods” which is contributing to a “growing regulatory pressure” [German, Online News, Sustainability and Ethics]. However, there is not a consensus on the merits of a plant-based diet, with some arguing that “the new industrial veganism is a rebranding of ultra-processed foods. It is a scam” [Spanish, Online News, Sustainability and Ethics].

Another way in which sustainable food is being discussed online is through discourse about eating seasonally. The benefits of seasonal food, such as how “choosing whole, seasonal produce grown nearby, helps strengthen food systems” [English, Online News, Cost of living and Home Cooking] and that “seasonal products from the homeland are generally cheaper” [German, Forum, Cost of living and Home Cooking] are shared online. Eating seasonally is supported through the provision of guidance, “The return of the market: discovering seasonal products: how to cook them, how to choose them, let’s open the baskets!” [French, Online News, Cost of Living and Home Cooking], access to local, seasonal goods through the restoration of markets, “including the reconstruction of the main city market” in a Czech municipality [Czech, Online News, Cost of Living and Home Cooking], and top-down practices from supermarkets, such as Intermarché who stopped selling imported strawberries and cherries in the winter, to encourage consumers to favour seasonal products [French, Forum, Cost of Living and Home Cooking].

6.2.3. Challenges for sustainable food

Alongside these discussions around the practices that can support the achievement of a sustainable food system, the social listening data also highlighted an awareness of ongoing challenges that affect the food system. Many of these challenges related to recent weather events and trends which impacted the agricultural sector. For example, discussions on the impact of droughts were prevalent within the data – “Agriculture has been affected by drought” [Spanish, Online News, Farming and Agriculture] and how there is a “weaker crop, for the fourth consecutive year, under the influence of severe droughts” [Croatian, Online News, Farming and Agriculture]. Both the impact on supply chains [English, Online News, Farming and Agriculture] and the resilience of natural ecology [English, Online News, Farming and Agriculture] were highlighted within the data.

Social barriers to sustainable food practices were also captured within the social listening data, with discussions about the higher costs of healthier, and more sustainable, foods [German, Online News, Sustainability and Ethics]. Within this, it suggests the importance of looking at the relationship between different practices and priority policy areas to ensure sufficient support is available – in this case, there is the need to look across both food and health sectors.

6.3. Linking the social listening analysis to the Sustainable Food experiment stream

As shown through the Meltwater data and the experiences of the SHARED GREEN DEAL Sustainable Food experiment, there is increasing interest in more sustainable food – ranging from agricultural processes to consumption practices. Yet, despite this interest in sustainable food, different stakeholders experience barriers to engaging with sustainable food. There is the need to address the barriers, including for example removing structural barriers related to choosing sustainable, healthy food options, and establishing market conditions to support local producers.

The challenges related to engaging with more sustainable food practices highlights the importance of establishing cross-sectoral responses and support mechanisms. There is the need to bring together different stakeholders to support the establishment of alternative practices, and cross-sectoral initiatives are required to support sustained, systemic change.

7. Sustainable Mobility

Highlights

- Online discourse about sustainable mobility focuses on the opportunities and challenges of different modes of low-carbon transport, including e-bikes, rail travel, and electric vehicles.
- Reference is made to the need to establish appropriate infrastructures to support sustainable mobility practices.
- The opportunities provided through alternative business models are received favourably within online discourse.

EV charging car sharing TGV Eurostar
 cargo bikes electric vehicle incentives e-bikes
 combustion engine bans second-life batteries
 superblocs battery swapping Frecciarossa
 high-speed rail rail travel car bans
 EV range anxiety vehicle-to-grid car-free living
 low-emission zones hybrid vehicles
 climate-friendly travel scenic train routes
 smart charging pedestrianisation
 cycling infrastructure 15-minute cities

Figure 7a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 7b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 7c. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords¹⁰

¹⁰ Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “millionen euro” [million euros], and therefore are not shown.

7.1. Introducing the Sustainable Mobility experiment stream

The Sustainable Mobility experiment stream developed context-specific interventions to support sustainable school commuting practices. These interventions were developed through Mobility Labs whereby insights from students, teachers and parents were captured. Further details on the experiment activities can be found in the [“Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools”](#) report (Haufe et al., 2025).

The involvement of different stakeholders affected by school commuting practices enabled innovative approaches for supporting sustainable commuting to be co-developed. Based upon insights obtained through the Mobility Labs, the following recommendations were developed: optimise public and school transport systems, with a focus on ensuring they are safe and sustainable; foster co-creative and multi-generational engagement around decision-making processes; promote sustainable mobility through legal and regulatory frameworks; integrate sustainable mobility into school curricula and support school mobility projects; and raise awareness of sustainable mobility more broadly.

The Meltwater search terms used for the social listening analysis were informed by the topics covered in the Sustainable Mobility experiment stream (Figure 7a). In particular the searches focused on “Car Use and Electrification”, “Rail Travel Renaissance” and “Urban Mobility”.

7.2. Key topics identified through social listening

7.2.1. Overview

Transport discussions were largely factual or policy-driven, and also carried emotional weight, particularly around issues such as climate legislation, infrastructure failures, and the future of electric vehicles. Sentiment analysis (Figure 7c) shows that the majority of mentions were neutral (82%), with positive sentiment accounting for 11% and negative sentiment 7.7%.

Key topics and words such as electric vehicles and public transport infrastructure highlighted the intersection of transport with everyday life, national policy, and environmental goals.

Geographically, Germany led the conversation with 32.9% of total, followed by the United Kingdom 19.5%, France 11.7%, Italy 9.09%, and Spain 7.45% (Figure 7b). Germany’s prominence may be linked to national debates around climate legislation and the future of car use.

7.2.2. E-Bikes

E-bikes were a commonly discussed topic online, with the discourse covering both the opportunities provided through this mode of transport, as well as the associated challenges. The environmental impact that turning towards an e-bike provides, rather than other forms of urban transportation, is discussed. A forum post highlighted research quantifying this impact, with “e-mopeds, e-bikes, and e-scooters [shown to] achieve reductions in CO2 emissions of 46%, 37%, and 21%, respectively, compared to other urban transportation” [German, Forum, Urban Mobility]. Indeed, a number of alternative business models that support the adoption of e-bikes are highlighted through the Meltwater analysis, including e-bike rentals [German, Forum, Urban Mobility]. These business models support the adoption of the more sustainable mode of transport.

However, the challenges and potential drawbacks of e-bikes is also shown within the Meltwater data. E-bikes are frequently referred to as a fire risk (“E-bikes are one of London’s fastest-growing fire risks” [English, Online News, Urban mobility]), with many online articles covering instances where an e-bike has resulted in a fire. For example, in Germany an online news article reported, “two e-bikes were being charged in the adjoining shed. The fire brigade prevented the fire from spreading.” [German, Online News, Urban mobility]. The hazards associated with e-bikes contribute to online materials advising on the best safety practices, including encouraging individuals to “only buy e-bikes, e-scooters and chargers and batteries from reputable retailers” [English, Online News, Urban Mobility] and “to store items containing lithium-ion batteries safely. Please charge any vehicles such as e-scooters, e-bikes or mobility scooters in a safe place, away from the exit pathways in your properties” [English, Blog, Urban Mobility]. The pollution associated with e-bike batteries was also captured within the social listening activity – “full of lithium batteries which, surprise, are not that clean after all” [French, Forum, Urban Mobility].

7.2.3. Rail travel

Rail travel was another mode of transport that was highly discussed online, including positive reflections on the advantages of travelling by train as well as negative sentiments that often related to disruptions.

The environmental advantages of travelling by train compared to other modes of transport were present within online discourse, as shown through this English news article, “rail travel is generally a comfortable, environmentally-friendly way of getting from A to B in Britain” [English, Online News, Rail Travel Renaissance]. As well as the economic advantages, particularly when tickets are booked in advance, “taking the Eurostar to Paris, can save you money compared to flights. European train systems offer great discounts for early bookings.” [English, online news, rail travel]. Yet, despite this, there were reflections within the data that there remain further opportunities to embrace rail travel, and that it was in fact “an underutilised option” [French, Online News, Rail Travel Renaissance].

Negative sentiments towards rail travel were also present within the Meltwater data, with this negative discourse centring around periods of disruption. Disruptions caused by strike action, infrastructure failures, and anti-social behaviour were discussed within the online discourse. The impact of rail strikes across various European countries including France, the UK, Italy, and Germany amongst others, was captured within the Meltwater data. For example, as reported within an online news article, “Christmas Rail Travel Faces Disruptions Amid Strikes and Staff Shortages.” [English, Online News, Rail Travel Renaissance]. Uncertainty underpinned many disruption-related discussions, including for example, “Deutsche Bahn will give a forecast on this at the earliest on Monday” [German, Forum, Rail Travel Renaissance].

Disruptions to rail services caused by infrastructural damage were also discussed online. As shown through a news article discussing how a storm in the UK “caused disruption across the county last weekend, impacting rail travel and leading to power outages at hundreds of properties” [English, Online News, Rail Travel Renaissance].

As the rail network spans Europe, there are many examples where coverage is provided for rail disruption beyond the country in which the disruption is occurring – “The line closure affects ICEs as well as the Eurostar to Brussels and Paris” [German, Forum, Rail Travel Renaissance]. This was also shown in coverage of the vandalism to the French TGV line ahead of the Paris Olympics, which received coverage across Europe – for example, “acts of sabotage and vandalism had been committed on several TGV lines just hours before the opening ceremony of the Olympic Games” [French, Online News, Rail Travel Renaissance] and “it was a coordinated sabotage of the French

TGV railway line on the day of the opening of the Olympic Games” [Czech, Online News, Rail Travel Renaissance]. The interconnections of the rail network as well as the global event contributed to a lot of discourse around this event.

7.2.4. Electric Vehicles

The growth of Electric Vehicles is shown within the Meltwater data, with a large online discourse around the required infrastructures and business models developed to support Electric Vehicles. There is a sentiment that “naturally, as consumer demand continues to grow, so will EV charging infrastructure” [English, Online News, Car Use and Electrification]. With this being supported through public funding [English, Online News, Car Use and Electrification] and also supporting the achievement of broader policy ambitions to reduce vehicle emissions [English, Online News, Car Use and Electrification].

Alongside the physical charging infrastructure for Electric Vehicles, there is also discourse around the socio-economic infrastructures supporting the adoption of Electric Vehicles. Across Europe, there is a growth in “schemes ranging from electric car sharing to car subscriptions, including rentals” [Italian, Online News, Car Use and Electrification], with online discourse promoting these opportunities including in the Netherlands, Italy and the UK.

Yet, despite the increasing adoption of Electric Vehicles, there remains a tension. For some, Electric Vehicles are not considered a priority investment as reflected in this French forum post, “If it were up to me, we would be exposed to upstream and midstream activities, electricity generation with gas plants, air freight and so on. But no, we have to invest in junk like EV charging, renewable energy and other green electron storage or where the business plan is rubbish but approved by the sustainability experts” [French, Forum, Car Use and Electrification]. The economic arguments for Electric Vehicles are also challenged within the online discourse, for example, “I wonder what arguments EV advocates will use once EVs are no longer subsidised by others and once a consumption tax is imposed on electricity for charging EVs” [Czech, Comment, Car Use and Electrification]. Within this, it highlights the complexity of developing sustainable mobility systems and the diverse viewpoints that exist.

7.3. *Linking the social listening analysis to the Sustainable Mobility experiment stream*

Whilst the social listening data did not focus solely on sustainable school commuting practices as was the case with the SHARED GREEN DEAL Sustainable Mobility experiment stream, the online discourse around different modes of transport align with the findings from the experiments. In general, there is a need to raise awareness of the alternative, low-carbon transport modes available.

The establishment of business models to support the adoption and utilisation of low-carbon modes of transport highlights the increased interest in these different modes of transport within society. Alongside these business models, there is the need to ensure that the supporting infrastructure – whether that be EV charging points or dedicated cycle lanes – are established. This aligns with insights obtained through the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment activities.

By ensuring that there are appropriate legal and regulatory frameworks in place, this can support the establishment and proliferation of low-carbon modes of transport, which in turn can help address other societal challenges including climate change and health.

8. SHARED GREEN DEAL cross-cutting themes

Each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments generated a great deal of qualitative data, from initial application forms to interviews with experiment participants, and reflections by local partners after the completion of the experiments. These helped to 'tell the story' of each experiment, and also enabled the consortium to carry out cross-cutting analysis on a number of important Social Science and Humanities (SSH) themes. These themes are: (1) Gender and Diversity; (2) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities; (3) Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19; (4) Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions and (5) Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time. Each of these cross-cutting analyses is presented as an open-access report on the SHARED GREEN DEAL website.

These cross-cutting analyses find clear resonance in the themes picked up by the Social Listening data, highlighting how attention to thematic topics such as gender, governance, justice and inclusion are fundamental to sustainability transitions across different sectors. The cross-cutting reports explore in some depth the mechanisms by which these themes influence the outcomes of transition processes, providing a useful complement to the Social Listening data which picks up the ways in which commentators in the online space are highlighting these influences

In this section, we present one key theme per cross-cutting topic from the social listening data, enabling us to 'hear from' online conversations on these topics and link these back to the insights emerging from the cross-cutting analyses.

8.1. Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities

procedural justice co-production toolkits policy design
 fair process stories of change funding barriers
 tick box participation cultural capital inclusive policy
 community building meaningful engagement
 exclusion vulnerable groups case studies inclusive innovation
 social capital community involvement
 grassroots participation access to decision-making
 marginalised communities barriers to participation
 decision-making small-scale organisations
 long-term engagement community organisations
 regulatory barriers best practices
 knowledge sharing funding fairness local equitable funding
 norms group formation

Figure 8a. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 8b. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 8c. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords¹¹

11 Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “últimos años” [recent years], and therefore are not shown.

8.1.1. Introducing the theme

This cross-cutting theme focussed on the efforts of SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments to foster meaningful engagement particularly of socioeconomically or culturally marginalised groups. The main questions addressed were around how this participation was ensured, what the challenges and barriers to engagement were and how experiment organisers overcame these. The analysis showed the great potential of co-production to bridge social and cultural divides, bringing together diverse groups to collectively address EU Green Deal challenges within their communities.

8.1.2. Overview of the social listening insights

The social listening data highlights that discourse around justice (found through our searches) (Figure 8a) were framed around issues of climate change, the European Green Deal, and the European Commission. Over the course of 2024, there were 648,000 mentions related to the topic of justice, with this being a 24.7% increase on the previous year. The total reach of these justice-related posts was 14.4 billion, yet despite the high number of outputs, the social echo decreased by nearly 70% compared to the previous year.

Whilst the sentiment of justice-related outputs were predominantly neutral (88%), there were slightly more positive sentiments (7.9%) compared to negative ones (3.2%) (Figure 8c). That being said, the emotional analysis highlighted a dominance of ‘sadness’. Negative feelings about justice also tended to focus on the impacts of climate change and the ‘coming years’ - i.e. the short and medium term future. Based upon this analysis, it suggests that there are more balanced discussions about justice within online spaces.

Keywords such as “European Commission”, “Green Deal”, “politiche a supporto” suggests that justice is viewed as an institutional issue within online discourse, indicating where responsibility for justice is perceived to be situated.

The online discourse on justice was dominated by Spain (43.9%), followed by the UK (17.3%), with Italy, France and Belgium all contributing similar levels of coverage (6.13%-7.89%) (Figure 8b).

8.1.3. The importance of citizen engagement with decision-making to ensure just transitions

One important theme within the online discourse was the need for ‘fairness’ and ‘engagement’ in Green Deal decision making. As one source highlighted, effective policy “requires fair participation in decision making, enabling vulnerable groups to participate” [English, Online News, Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities]. A proportion of these mentions pertain to normative arguments in favour of meaningful inclusion particularly of marginalised groups. For example, highlighting the recognition that it is at community level that effective policies are driven and operationalised. As one blog source highlighted: “communities are at the heart of effective environmental change and climate policy shifts are often driven by local communities’ voices... These initiatives contribute to building a global movement of engaged citizens” [English, Blog post, Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities]. Other sources are reports or descriptions of projects describing the nature and qualities of citizens’ engagement or showcasing projects which bring communities together.

The importance of engaging deeply with citizens’ concerns is underscored by the need to understand people’s perceptions of policies and the implications of this for policy support and citizen

engagement. Projects mentioned in these examples highlighted the links between co-creation and effectiveness, by describing how engagement leads to better identification of citizens' needs.

Some mentions highlight the importance of deeper citizen engagement in contexts where citizens may experience trade-offs, such as between climate protection and energy prices. As one German language news platform reported for example: "The EU's climate policy is particularly controversial: in [a] survey, participants were asked to find a hypothetical compromise between the two goals of climate protection on the one hand and the avoidance of the increase in energy costs on the other. In most countries – with the exception of Sweden and Portugal – respondents would rather reduce energy costs instead of following climate protection measures." [German, Online News, Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities]. Others highlight how important justice-focused themes such as the Green Deal may be associated with significant polarisation; the implication for associated policy making is that efforts towards inclusivity and co-creation are essential.

8.1.4. Linking back to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments

The SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments did not engage substantively with issues of social polarisation around the Green Deal, but instead, offered spaces where citizens could engage deeply with Green Deal challenges as these unfold within their unique contexts. Through these efforts, it became clear to participants and organisers alike that efforts to foster inclusion have improved outcomes and qualitatively impacted the reach and potential of each experiment (Bharucha, 2025). This aligns with the online discourse that argues for the meaningful inclusion of different communities (in particular, marginalised groups) within decision making processes around sustainability action.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments showed *how* the practical organisation of participatory processes may be effectively set up across the very different sociocultural contexts of the EU. Similar sentiments were identified within the social listening data - the complex interactions and trade-offs associated with sustainability actions demonstrate the need for intentional communication and opportunities to co-create actions to support their success. Testimonies from non-profit organisations and local municipalities involved in the organisation of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments show that great care and attention is needed in order to foster a convivial and collaborative group, but once this is accomplished, citizen participants from all walks of life, including those from marginalised groups, form highly motivated and effective teams.

8.2. Gender and Diversity

Figure 8d. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 8e. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)¹²

¹² Due to the diverse ways in which gender is discussed within online discourse, the key words included within the sentiment analysis were not relevant to the SHARED GREEN DEAL topic or the analysis undertaken so we have not presented the sentiment analysis.

8.2.1. Introducing the theme

The cross-cutting analysis on gender explored the ways in which SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments were designed and run in gender-sensitive ways, and the interaction of gender with other issues related to structural inequalities, in shaping engagement, practical actions and outcomes. Gender within this analysis was considered in terms of gender dynamics within the experiments, gendered understandings and know-how and how these manifested within the projects. The analysis also considered the gendering of experiments' spaces and communications and gendered dimensions of practices and performances within the experiments. The analysis identified a number of ways in which gender-sensitivity was incorporated into the experiments, as well as usefully highlighting challenges such as the pervasive influence of gender stereotypes and difficulties with ensuring adequate representation of structurally vulnerable groups.

8.2.2. Overview of the social listening insights

The Meltwater data (Figure 8d) shows increasing gender-related mentions, with a 72% increase on the previous year with 1.39 million mentions in 2024. The online discourse around gender has a reach of 1.54 trillion with this being comparable to the previous year. However, the social echo has decreased to 9.72 million, from 52.2 million last year.

Just over three-quarters of the gender-related outputs were of neutral sentiment (77%), with there being more negative sentiment (14%) than positive sentiment (9.1%) across the data. A range of emotions were identified within the data, including sadness, disgust, anger, joy, and love.

Keywords such as “roles de género” [gender roles], “godine” [years], and “dana” [days] highlight the various spaces and timescales within which gender is discussed online and showcases the complexity of gender issues across Europe.

A third of gender-related mentions were from Serbia (33.5%), with this being over double the amount of mentions within the country with the next highest amount of mentions (Croatia, 14.1%) (Figure 8e).

8.2.3. The persistence of gendered roles and practices

The social listening data highlighted the continued existence of gender-divisions in everyday life, and some recognise these as important influences on the shape of evolving green transitions. Going beyond this, it is recognised that gender-based disparities still shape certain important sectors that are crucial to the green transition. For example, commenting on the disparities in women's representation within certain economic sectors, one news article highlights: “Disparities persist in particular with an unequal distribution between trades, an absence in the roles of manufacturing managers and an under-representation in certain sectors. Indeed... the construction sectors remain predominantly male’ [French, News Article, Gender and Diversity]. Further, it is recognised that stereotypes and gender-based divisions may be further perpetuated by the application of new AI technologies, “undermining women's representation and opportunities” [English, News article, Gender and Diversity].

Women have reported within our SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments how the gendering of everyday life shapes their ability to participate in civic processes and in co-production. This theme was reflected in some of the some of the material within our social listening exercises wherein posts highlighted the involvement of women in household chores. Other mentions report on the

successes achieved by women who engaged for the first time in civic or collective endeavours, sometimes for the first time and in doing so, subverting traditional gender-based expectations. For example, describing the impacts of a new cooperative set up in Turkiye, a news article reported: “the cooperative has not only provided a source of income but has also challenged traditional gender roles within households. When women say they are going out of the house to make money, they are respected more by their spouses... When they get back home, the sharing of household labour is easier” [English, News Article, Gender and Diversity].

8.2.4. Linking back to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments

The SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment showed the continued influence of gender divisions on sustainability transitions. In response, the SHARED GREEN DEAL analysis on gender recommends early and sustained attention to gender when social initiatives are planned (Aggeli et al. 2025). The analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments highlighted how pervasive gendered social expectations remain across different European contexts, as well as how women are disproportionately impacted by social inequalities. Resonating closely with the social listening data, the analysis highlights how everyday communication and the spaces in which initiatives are carried out may shape participation. Indeed, the analysis highlighted how better outcomes are achieved when these are factored in at the planning stage, and when inclusive learning and communication is fostered.

8.3. Geographic Differences and Evolutions Across Time

Figure 8f. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 8g. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 8h. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords¹³

13 Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “rôle essentiel” [essential role], and therefore are not shown.

8.3.1. Introducing the theme

This cross-cutting theme analysed the influence of local conditions across different European contexts on the outcomes of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments. An underlying theme across the experiments has been that community building and grassroots action is essential to success in implementing sustainability transitions (see also Bharucha 2025). This suggests a powerful influence of local contextual factors which shape how initiatives are received and adopted (Nieboer et al. 2025). The theme further explored how different contexts across Europe either fostered or hindered scaling of the SHARED GREEN DEAL initiatives, whether this was local scaling or even in a few cases, at regional or national scale. Scaling occurred through either *growing* the initiative through more examples in a similar context ('growing'), or through the adoption of the same kind of initiative in a dissimilar context ('replicating'). Scaling examples also covered instances of knowledge sharing with other initiatives or the transfer of methodologies. In addition to identifying these examples of scaling, the analysis also explored the influence of social or institutional conditions, market factors and coordination amongst local actors as either barriers or enablers of scaling. A key learning point in this analysis was the tremendous potential of grassroots initiatives in fostering change and can readily scale if given the right support.

8.3.2. Overview of the social listening insights

The Social Listening data highlights increased interest in and online reach of outputs focused on geographic and institutional differences. There is a 65.5% increase in mentions of these topics within social outputs compared to the previous year, with the total reach of these outputs increasing by 41.9% to 19.6 billion. Despite this growth, the social echo of the outputs decreased by 35.9% to 61,000.

Although the majority of online discourse related to geographic and institutional differences was analysed by the Meltwater platform to be neutral, over a quarter of the online discourse contributions about geography were positive (26%). Positive sentiments related to topics such as the "travail des élus locaux" [the work of local elected officials], "efforts de conservation" [conservation efforts], "communauté locale" [local community] and "démarche de proximité" [a community-based approach]. A small proportion of the online discourse was analysed as being of negative sentiments (2.5%).

The key words for the cross-cutting theme of Geographic and Institutional Differences capture the scales at which sustainability action is occurring across Europe and the mechanisms underpinning this action, including "grassroots initiatives", "local approach", "work of elected officials", and "financial support".

Over half of the mentioned related to geographic and institutional differences are from France (52.1%) with just over a fifth of mentions coming from Spain (22.4%).

8.3.3. Support for growing grassroots initiatives in Europe

The Social Listening data highlighted a number of mentions of initiatives funding grassroots initiatives through for example small grants programmes, including initiatives by the private sector, demonstrating confidence in this approach to addressing societal challenges and making "tangible change". Mentions also touched on the influence of grassroots initiatives in specifically benefiting otherwise underserved communities - such as for example providing grants to foster participation in sports for children. Tying into this theme are also examples of initiatives which foster a

place-based approach to development, for example, through place-based sustainable tourism initiatives which engage closely with local communities, aiming to foster local development and landscape preservation in addition to economic development. It is recognised that supporting grassroots initiatives can lead to scaling changes in communities, even if this is simply via deepening knowledge: “By educating yourself, you can become an advocate for sustainable solutions in your community” [Spanish, News article, Geographic Differences and Evolutions across Time].

8.3.4. Linking back to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments

Whilst the Social Listening exercises did not specifically focus on grassroots initiatives and variations in the outcomes of these across different European contexts, it did strongly reinforce the overall message from the SHARED GREEN DEAL cross-cutting analysis about the importance and potential of these initiatives. As the analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments highlighted, grassroots initiatives are key to the kinds of change need to implement the European Green Deal. These initiatives show great potential to catalyse this and then even scale further to regional or national level if given the right support. The value of local action to support the achievement of sustainability ambitions was present within the online discourse, with a range of initiatives utilising different approaches and addressing different challenges present within the social listening data. One encouraging implication is that change can occur even with relatively low levels of investment; it is thus encouraging that the Social Listening exercise highlighted many examples showcasing investment and grant programmes to enable projects.

8.4. Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions

Figure 8i. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 8j. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 8k. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords

8.4.1. Introducing the theme

This theme analysed how community-scale action translates the governance agenda of the Green Deal at local level. The evidence from the social experiments showed that when local actors link up initiatives with ongoing local governance processes, they can drive lasting change. A key enabler of this is relationship building, as well as organisational and institutional learning which helps build capacity to deal with unexpected challenges. The analysis showed that a variety of different innovations can help local communities to influence governance agendas for sustainability, including educational innovations, reconfiguring relationships, restructuring of local organisations to help build capacity and finding new ways to contribute to policy. These innovations can, it was found, help change the way that sustainability challenges are governed locally by government authorities, non-governmental organisations, communities, and businesses (Gray et al., 2025b).

8.4.2. Overview of the social listening insights

Online mentions related to governance agendas (Figure 8i) totalled 646,000 in 2024, with this being an increase of 14.1% on the previous year. Despite this increase in mentions, the total reach of posts decreased by 8.69% to 13 billion and the social echo decreased by 73% in comparison to the previous year.

Most of the online discourse about governance agendas was analysed as neutral by the Meltwater platform (87%), with 9.8% of posts analysed as positive and only 2.9% as negative. A number of topics had were discussed in a positive, negative and neutral way by different sources, including the European Commission, climate change, and industry (Figure 8k). This highlights the range of perceptions held across Europe in relation to governance, and the complexity of the topic.

The keywords related to governance in the Meltwater data included the “European Commission”, “grandes empresas” [large companies], “implementation”, “climate neutrality”, “development projects” and “energy transition”. These keywords focus on strategic visions and the achievement of low-carbon ambitions, as well as touching on the key stakeholders to be involved in these processes.

The country with the most mentions related to governance was Spain (31.2%), potentially a by-product of the local elections that took place there in 2024. Both France and the UK also had relatively higher levels of interaction with the theme of governance, contributing to 16.6% and 16.3% of mentions respectively (Figure 8j).

8.4.3. Governing the Green Deal for equitable outcomes

One important theme in the social listening data is the importance of governing the Green Deal so that legislation works for everyone. Mentions for example highlight the presence of varied and sometimes competing interests: As one example highlights: “For the Green Deal to become a reality, it has to work for everyone. It cannot be something only for those who can afford it. We need to ease the transition and help people, to leave no one behind” [English, News article, Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions]. Others provide examples of areas where adaptations are required in order to ensure that the Green Deal works for everyone. One example comes from farmer strikes and protests in response to agricultural policy. Another instance is the example of small businesses facing burdensome reporting requirements to comply with emissions reduction targets. In a related vein, other Mentions highlight the need for careful and clear implementation guidelines in order to keep industry compliant with legislation, suggesting the need for careful liaising between private and public sectors so that implementation guidelines can be crafted in

ways that are clear to private sector actors operating at all scales. A key implication is that governing for the Green Deal needs a multistakeholder approach that brings together “local authorities, entrepreneurs, researchers, and NGOs on best practices for fostering community relations” [English, News article, Governance Agendas, Framings and Conventions].

8.4.4. Linking back to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments

The SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments showed that there are a number of barriers to long-term change which emerge from the context-specificities of governance structures. Some of these barriers mean that trade-offs may not be well-managed or that recommendations made by careful co-production in multi-stakeholder platforms may not necessarily get policy traction. The Social Listening data highlighted the existence of these barriers as well, touching on social, economic and regulatory barriers to sustainability transitions.

An important recommendation is therefore that the kinds of issues picked up in the social listening exercise need careful and sustained attention within Green Deal policy making, with well-crafted mechanisms in place to overcome governance-related barriers to change. Giving people a real ‘voice’ in Green Deal policy making, as was the intention in many of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments, must be a priority, aligning with many of the lessons learned across the cross-cutting analysis.

8.5. Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19

Figure 81. Word cloud representing the search terms used (in English), these were translated into 9 further languages

Figure 8m. Top 5 countries with the most coverage (quantified by mentions of search terms during 2024)

Figure 8n. Sentiment analysis of most used keywords¹⁴

14 Some top 10 terms were less relevant to the analysis, e.g. “report”, and therefore are not shown.

8.5.1. Introducing the theme

This final cross-cutting analysis explored how societal challenges emerging after the coronavirus pandemic can either foster or hinder progress in the implementation of the Green Deal. These societal challenges include a broad spectrum of so-called ‘wicked’ problems that have deepened immediately following the pandemic, including These include digitalisation of provisioning systems, advances in Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence, changing patterns of work, changes to urban planning such as the revival of ideas such as the 15-minute city, and significant geopolitical conflicts such as the Ukraine-Russia war, and in West Asia. The analysis highlights a number of recommendations for supporting niche level innovations such as the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments in a way that allows them to contribute to systemic resilience as well as enhanced capacity to respond to the complex terrain of social, political, technological and economic changes shaping Europe (Truninger et al., 2025).

8.5.2. Overview of the social listening insights

The total number of mentions touching on societal challenges (Figure 8l) increased significantly (168%) compared to the previous year, with 209 million mentions. Despite this high level of growth, the total reach of these online outputs only increased marginally by 2.35%. The social echo of societal challenges decreased by 88% to 752 million.

Although nearly two-thirds of the online discourse on societal challenges was neutral, almost a quarter of the online discourse about societal challenges was analysed as being negative – with these negative sentiments relating to topics of “government”, “money” and “children” (Figure 8n). That being said, 12% of the discourse was classified as positive, with this highlighting the diverse views on this topic that exist within the online space.

The keywords identified through the Meltwater analysis cover a range of topics, including “country”, “government”, “life”, “work”, “benefits”, and “family”, with this diversity of topics potentially a result of the complex and varied societal challenges experienced within Europe.

Four countries dominate the online discourse around societal challenges: Spain (44%), France (15%), the UK (13.5%), and Germany (12.2%) (Figure 8m).

8.5.3. Recognition of cross-cutting societal challenges

One key theme from the social listening data was the recognition of the broad-ranging challenges that face societies across Europe since the pandemic, and the multiple pressures that communities and citizens must navigate as a result. The implication of some of these mentions was the need for adaptive policy making that would help people to navigate change. Examples included challenges stemming from the rising cost of living requiring changes to taxes and subsidies. Some of the mentions demonstrate a policy-level recognition of how interlinked societal challenges combine to create significant social pressure. For example, as one highlights, families face: “difficulties with education, with poor housing, with living standards, with the cost of living and employment” [English, News article, Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19]. Mentions highlight the need to build systemic resilience and highlight both social and economic factors as well as the potential challenges which may stem from a changing climate. Examples include commentaries on the future functioning of transport infrastructure in the context of floods or storms. Other mentions highlight policy initiatives targeted at these complex challenges, such as changes to social security, efforts to improve housing and other investments in community development.

A related theme was the need to improve trust between communities and government at all levels, in the context of dynamic and complex societal challenges. For example, as one mention highlighted: “...raising taxes to spend money on infrastructure means you’ve got to trust the people doing the spending” [English, News article, Societal Challenges Post-COVID-19].

8.5.4. Linking back to the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments

SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments showed the extent to which interlinked societal challenges have deepened since the Covid-19 pandemic. The cross-cutting analysis on societal challenges within the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments highlighted the systemic and overlapping nature of challenges which seem to have accelerated since the COVID-19 pandemic. In resonance with the social listening data, this analysis highlighted the need for building anticipatory governance through tools such as participatory foresight, community visioning and scenario planning, as well as the need to make these processes as inclusive as possible. This speaks in part to the recognition within the social listening data on the importance of building trust between citizens and government at all scales and supporting community-level initiatives to foster long-term transformation.

9. Conclusions and reflections for policy and governance

9.1. Early reflections on policy and social listening

This final section reflects on what these SHARED GREEN DEAL findings imply for the design, implementation and governance of EU sustainability policies within the current EU mandate, with particular focus on the role of bottom-up approaches and community involvement in delivering a sustainable, just transition. This report uses the social listening findings to reflect on how sustainability issues have been framed and discussed in local media, social media across Europe, including countries that did not host any SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments. Whilst the social listening analysis provides indicative signals and discourse context, it is important to note that it is not representative of public opinion or evidence of behaviour change.

The social listening exercise was designed to complement social experiments by engaging wider online discourse on the works streams beyond location and participation to SHARED GREEN DEAL project. It is important to point out that, while the social listening was done in 10 EU languages, it inevitably cannot cover the entire geographical scope for EU policies, and it results in some countries appearing more prominently than others. As such, the social listening exercise is seen more as indicative signals rather than specific evidence.

With this in mind, the reflections stemming from SHARED GREEN DEAL insights are situated within an increasing political contestation around sustainability policy, where tensions are raised due to concerns about the affordability of such policies, the consequences for EU competitiveness and security, and growing emphasis on policy delivery under the current EU mandate towards shaping and advancing sustainability in the Union. In this context, the findings of SHARED GREEN DEAL and the social listening address these pressures, underlining the importance of governance functions prioritising trust, participation, and the relevance of action at the community level. These actions are needed and complementary to a regulatory approach and to market-based instruments, which are, or should be, part of an adjusted policy-mix.

Across the experimental streams and through the social listening exercise, citizens engage with sustainability in their daily lives: mobility choices, housing conditions, food affordability, and energy costs. On one hand, bottom-up initiatives linking policy goals to citizens' concerns support the practice of translating abstract targets into concrete solutions. On the other hand, where sustainability policies are perceived as distant or far-fetched, even imposed, public resistance or disinterest is likely to appear. The results of the present report further reinforce the considerations brought by our previous publications assessing the role of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiments in advancing Climate action and Zero Pollution, shedding light on the crucial role that better policy coordination, tailored support for vulnerable groups, improved data on local climate contributions, and long-term resources for participatory action can play.

This brings us to a key point: implementation capacity is not just a technical or regulatory issue, it is a social one. If environmental policies fail to meaningfully engage communities, they are at risk of losing their legitimacy, even when their rationale is clear.

9.2. Cross-cutting governance insights

Local knowledge, trust and legitimacy are the needed infrastructure for policy implementation.

As it emerged from SHARED GREEN DEAL results analysing efficient renovations, energy issues, and circular economy principles, the role of intermediaries to disseminate trusted knowledge is much valued at the local level. Knowledge networks, eco-tours or peer-to-peer learning combined technical information with local relevance and in-person experience. Online discourse also showed the importance of spaces like fora, social media and local media in shaping knowledge and confidence around sustainability practices. An important implication is that policy delivery needs not only technical guidance, but a solid social infrastructure that should be recognised and supported accordingly.

Abstract goals should be grounded in local benefits. Findings indicate that what appears to be a less concrete sustainability goal should become a tangible outcome that mirrors local needs. This means that raising awareness about sustainability policies, priorities and solutions should become a day-to-day practice. For instance, circular economy is being discussed with household budgets and activities, or clean energy is framed through energy independence and resilience. Therefore, local interpretation and adaptation of policies through targeted citizen engagement are not add-ons to the regulatory framework, but necessary tools for effective governance.

Sustainability action is connected to societal challenges. Evidence from social listening and local insights frames sustainability measures together with social issues: cost of living, health and inequality, energy poverty, among others. SHARED GREEN DEAL experiences stressed the importance of integrated policy responses against siloed approaches. Renovation initiatives address energy efficiency, or food experiments link environmental sustainability with health, for instance. This suggests an increasing need for coordination across policy domains, with funding streams carefully integrated and planned together.

Institutions should foster dialogue and co-production with citizens. Participatory processes, like community visioning, study circles, mobility labs, are highly valued and pivotal in navigating tensions since different perspectives can be explained and trade-offs openly discussed. This approach is particularly useful to adopt in the presence of polarised policy environments, and social listening data reinforced this finding. As such, dialogue and co-production help manage conflict, can reduce resistance and increase durability.

9.3. What are the implications for EU policy frameworks and multi-level governance?

We now consider what this means for the translation from policy design to policy delivery. Several policy instruments at the EU level (such as Horizon Europe, Cohesion Policy, LIFE funding, CAP, among others) already support local actions. Across several EU examples that already support local action, the challenge stands in how existing policy frameworks can increase coordination, accessibility and operability across different scales.

A first implication is the need to shift the focus from isolated interventions towards more continuous support for local capacity. Fragmented funding programmes can hinder communities' ability to keep momentum and scale up successful practices. If continuity and coherence across funding

mechanisms are ensured, bottom-up innovation can work more consistently over time and across different realities.

A change is needed to enable EU-to-local translation at the national level. Evidence points to the fact that national frameworks strongly shape what is locally achievable. This means that the EU holds potential to provide flexible policy instruments, allowing for local adaptation while supporting and fostering experimentation across topics.

Multi-level governance needs to be strengthened. A more fluid and continuous vertical dialogue is key, where EU can interact and speak through national levels to local ones, translating EU and national priorities into community-level actions. To do so, actors such as municipalities, well-placed NGOs and trusted networks play a fundamental role. This highlights the need to support governance capacity, not just outcomes.

9.4. Shifting from a Green Deal to a Clean, Industrial deal and beyond

Taken together, the results of this report suggest that community-level involvement is a core governance principle to foster climate action and achieve zero pollution. Communities, and meso-level interventions which operate between 'individuals' and 'systems', are core sources of innovation. Bottomup approaches contribute to shift policy approach towards a more local level, enhancing their legitimacy, letting citizens act as partners rather than passive recipients. With this in mind, and with the evidence collected by the social listening and the main results of the project, it is clear that future sustainability policies should treat community-level initiatives as core components of their implementation strategies.

10. References

- Aggeli, A., Wieser, P., Heffernan, R., Wiedmann, F. 2025. Gender and Intersectional Diversity structures that shape the EU Green Deal. In: Truninger, M.; Disterheft, A.; Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762546>
- Beers, P.J., van Bellen, L., Carraca, J., Girardi, A., Gritti, V., Hebinck, A., Kiewik, J., Mourato, J., Nieboer, S., Silvestri, G., Truninger, M., 2025. Scaling food systems transitions. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15369887>
- Bharucha, Z.P. 2025. Exploring themes of justice, vulnerability and inequality in social innovation processes for the European Green Deal. In: Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762555>
- European Commission, N.D. The European Green Deal. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en [accessed: 08/05/2026].
- European Economic and Social Committee, 2024. EESC calls for recalibration of the EU Green Deal to address emerging challenges. <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/news-media/news/eesc-calls-recalibration-eu-green-deal-address-emerging-challenges> [accessed: 15/05/2026].
- Foulds, C., Royston, S., Crowther, A., Aggeli, A., Robison, R., Noreña Ospina, M., Wieser, P., 2025. Bringing together citizens and professionals to develop know-how for energy efficient renovations. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270137>
- Gray, E. K., Rohse, M., Fahy, F., Jost, C., 2025a. Community visioning for just, clean energy futures in Europe. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270128>
- Gray, E. K., Fahy, F., Kovács, K. 2025b. Governing the European Green Deal Through Local Social Experiments. In: Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762512>
- Haufe, N., Tönkö, A. 2025. Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315291>
- Martin, B., Robison, R., Truninger, M., Crowther, A. 2026. *Scaling green transitions: using social listening to explore Green Deal online discourse across Europe. Methodological Appendix*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20085510>

- McGowan, B.S. 2022. World Health Organization's Early AI-supported Response with Social Listening Platform. *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, 110(2), pp. 73-275. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jmla.2022.1398>
- Nieboer, S., Hansmeier, H., Beers, P.J., Seus, S., Hebinck, A. 2025. The Impact of Geographical Enablers and Barriers on the Scaling of Grassroots Innovation Initiatives. In: Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J. (eds). *Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762521>
- Parks, E.S., Faw, M.H., Lane, L.R. 2024. *Listening: The key concepts*. London: Routledge.
- Ruiz, H., Katusic, V., Hamika S., 2025. Implementing Local Accelerator Hubs to foster business innovation in the circular economy. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): *Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270150>
- Šmid Hribar, M., Ribeiro, D., Strasser, S., Paliogiannis, H., 2025. Exploring the Study Circle approach in fostering change in biodiversity values among adults. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): *Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270156>
- Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J., Bujeda, J. 2025. Societal challenges and the Green Deal in Europe Post-Coronavirus. In: Truninger, M.; Disterheft, A.; Carraça, J. (eds). *Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762528>

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